

A simple method of producing green manure *Sesbania rostrata* to achieve N synchrony in lowland rice

G. Seneviratne and E.M.H.G.S. Ekanayake, Biological Nitrogen Fixation Project, IFS, Kandy, Sri Lanka
E-mail: gaminis@ifs.ac.lk

There is concern, particularly in the tropics, that some high-quality leguminous green manures (LGM) and crop residues may release nitrogen (N) into the soil so rapidly that losses of N may occur through denitrification, ammonia volatilization, and leaching. In Sri Lanka, for example, it is reported that as much as 75% of *Sesbania rostrata*-N is lost in dry-zone lowland soils (Seneviratne and Kulasoorya 1994). The concept of synchrony of N supply with crop demand has thus resulted. An organic material of the right quality may release N at approximately the same time and rate required by the crop, thereby reducing N losses. This has been tested by mixing low- and high-quality plant materials in different proportions (Myers et al 1994). However, this method adds an additional cost to green manuring because of the labor involved in transporting and applying plant materials with a high C:N ratio. This study investigated a simple cultural method to produce low- and high-quality green manures *in situ* with *S. rostrata*.

The study was conducted in two farmers' fields (sites 1 and 2) of the low-country intermediate zone of Sri Lanka during the fallow period before the 1998

dry season. Soil in the area was a Tropaqualf with pH 6.4, organic carbon (C) 1.2%, total N 0.06%, and available phosphorus (P) 9.5 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil. Fifteen plots of 6 × 3 m were prepared in three rows, with five plots per row at each site. They were surrounded by 45-cm-wide bands. Irrigation canals were constructed between rows. Five seeding rates of *S. rostrata* ranging from 100 to 300 kg ha⁻¹ were applied in a completely randomized design with three replications (see table). Plots were puddled, leveled, and pretreated with concentrated H₂SO₄ for 7 min and allowed to stay this way overnight, and inoculated (with *Azorbizobium caulinodans* ORS 571) seeds were broadcast evenly onto moist soil. Basal dressings of K and P were applied at 16.6 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ and 11 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹, respectively. After a week, plots were flooded to about 3-cm depth. Stem inoculation with the rhizobial strain was carried out 2, 4, and 6 wk after broadcast by sprinkling broth onto the shoot. When plants were 9 wk old, three samples of whole plants were carefully uprooted from 1 × 1-m squares from each plot. Root systems were washed and plant number was

counted. Samples were then oven-dried (65 °C for 72 h), weighed, and ground. Ground subsamples were analyzed for total N by the Kjeldahl method. C content was calculated as 45% of the plant dry weight.

Because of the lower coefficient of variation (CV) at site 1 compared with site 2, different seed rates at the first site produced significantly different plant densities and biomass (see table). The higher the plant density, the higher the biomass and the lower the plant dry weight at both sites. N concentration also declined under higher plant densities. N accumulation was highest at plant densities of 44–46 × 10⁵ ha⁻¹ at the two sites. C:N ranged from 16 to 19 at plant densities below 6 × 10⁵ ha⁻¹ and increased sharply up to about 40 at plant densities of 44–53 × 10⁵ ha⁻¹. The C:N achieved here for low and high plant densities is ideal for attaining synchrony because it was shown recently that tropical litter with C:N below and above 27 has contrasting N dynamics, that is, net mineralization and immobilization, respectively (Seneviratne 2000).

This study showed that green manure quality of *S. rostrata* can easily be

Growth parameters and green manure quality of *Sesbania rostrata* under different seeding rates in two farmers' field^a sites.

Seeding rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	Plant density (× 10 ⁵ ha ⁻¹)		Biomass production (t dry matter ha ⁻¹)		Plant dry weight (g)		N (%)		N accumulation (kg ha ⁻¹)		C:N	
	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
100	2.8 e	2.9 b	2.4 e	2.3 d	8.57	7.93	2.71	2.47	65	57	16.6	18.2
140	4.0 d	3.7 b	2.8 d	2.5 cd	7.00	6.76	2.75	2.32	77	58	16.4	19.4
210	6.0 c	5.6 b	3.8 c	3.1 c	6.33	5.54	2.76	2.61	105	81	16.3	17.2
250	44.4 b	46.2 a	10.5 b	9.8 b	2.36	2.12	1.76	1.41	185	138	25.6	31.9
300	52.5 a	49.6 a	11.3 a	10.7 a	2.15	2.16	1.28	1.13	145	121	35.2	39.8
LSD (0.05)	0.97	3.50	0.29	0.73	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
CV (%)	2.36	8.64	2.46	6.86	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

^aValues in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% probability level. LSD = least significant difference, CV = coefficient of variation, S1 = site 1, S2 = site 2.

changed by varying its plant density. This has an important implication for achieving synchrony with *in situ* green manure crops. In practice, linear alternate plots of low and high plant densities in the field can produce green manure with contrasting quality. Green manure produced in this manner can be mixed and incorporated during land preparation to achieve better

synchrony between N release and demand in lowland rice.

References

Myers RJK, Palm CA, Cuevas E, Gunatilleke IUN, Brossard M. 1994. The synchronization of nutrient mineralization and plant nutrient demand. In: Woomer PL, Swift MJ, editors. *The biological management of tropical soil fertility*. Chichester (UK): Wiley. p 81–116.

Seneviratne G. 2000. Litter quality and nitrogen release in tropical agriculture: a synthesis. *Biol. Fert. Soils* 31:60–64.

Seneviratne G, Kulasoorya SA. 1994. Fate of applied N in traditional, modern, and conservation farming systems of lowland rice in Sri Lanka. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 19(1):18–19.

Low-cost management of iron toxicity in farmers' fields in Sierra Leone

I. Baggie and A.R. Bah, Rice Research Station, PMB 736, Freetown, Sierra Leone

Iron (Fe) toxicity affects up to 60% of the total cultivable inland valley swamps (IVS) in West Africa and reduces grain yield by up to 80%. Resource-poor farmers cannot afford to use high-cost technologies such as chemical amendments to reduce Fe toxicity. Over the years, on-station experiments have shown the great potential of organic amendments and toxicity-tolerant rice genotypes to improve Fe-toxic soils in the IVS. However, their adaptability in farmers' fields with varying soil types, water regimes, and extent and severity of Fe toxicity needs to be evaluated.

Two types of trials (to determine the effects of variety and organic amendment) were conducted on Fe-toxic IVS at 12 sites in Sierra Leone in the 1995–96 and 1996–97 seasons. Farmer groups from four villages participated. The soil characteristics varied and were in these ranges: 3.8–5.3 for pH in water, 3.6–4.1 for pH in KCl, 0.07–0.35% N, 0.4–3.5 mg Bray-1 P kg⁻¹ soil, 7.2–13.2% organic C, 3.1–6.9% Fe₂O₃, 31–75% sand, 12–31% silt, and 11–38% clay.

The first-season trials were managed by both farmers and researchers, whereas the second-season trials were farmer-managed. In the first trials, two rice genotypes, one tolerant (ROK24) and one

susceptible (ROK5), were grown unreplicated with the farmers' variety in 120-m² plots. Four-week-old seedlings were transplanted at 0.15 × 0.2-m spacing. Only N as urea was applied uniformly at 10 kg ha⁻¹. Iron toxicity ratings were scored 7 wk after transplanting using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) developed at IRRI. Harvesting was done at physiological maturity; materials were sun-dried and weighed and the grain yield adjusted to 14% moisture content. The second trials involved three treatments with organic amendment (5t *Calopogonium mucunoides* ha⁻¹, 5t partially decomposed rice husk ha⁻¹, and the control [no amendment]) using the farmers' variety as the test variety. Urea was also applied at 10 kg N ha⁻¹ and data were collected with the same method used in the first trials.

The selected sites were acidic and had low available P and high Fe. Tolerant genotype ROK24 significantly outyielded susceptible genotype ROK5 (Table 1). The mean grain yield increase in ROK24 over that of susceptible ROK5 and the local check was 90.4% and 57.6%, respectively. Overall, yields were higher in the first season than in the second season, presumably because of differences in management.

Incorporation of 5 t ha⁻¹ partially decomposed rice husk or *C. mucunoides* increased grain yield over the control by 76% and 77%, respectively (Table 2). This proves the ameliorating power of organic residues to correct Fe toxicity. Higher grain yield corresponds to lower Fe toxicity scores and vice versa, indicating a strong negative association between severity of Fe

Table 1. Varietal differences in response to iron toxicity in farmers' fields over two seasons.^a

Variety	Effective tillers m ⁻² (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
ROK24 (tolerant)	95	1.5 (3)
ROK5 (susceptible)	53	0.8 (7)
Local	59	0.9 (5)
CV (%)	15.4	24
Variety	11	0.2
Site (replication)	***	***
Season (year)	**	**

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate Fe toxicity score by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). ** and *** = statistically significant at 1% and 0.1%, respectively.